

NECROBACTERIOSIS OF HIGH-YIELDING CATTLE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17907045>

Abstract. This article presents the results of clinical, epizootiological, and laboratory studies of necrobacteriosis in high-yielding cattle. The research identified the main factors influencing the spread of the disease as high humidity, contamination of skin and hooves, non-compliance with sanitary-hygienic standards, and deficiency of biogenic elements in the diet.

In affected cattle, lameness accompanied by inflammation, swelling, and pain in the hoof region was observed. Laboratory analyses isolated *Fusobacterium necrophorum* as the primary causative agent of necrobacteriosis.

Based on the findings, preventive and effective treatment methods were proposed. In particular, adherence to zoohygienic standards, regular hoof care, disinfection with antiseptic agents, and supplementation of feed with biotin and selenium significantly reduced the spread of the disease in experimental trials.

Key words: Cattle, necrobacteriosis, hoof diseases, lameness, *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, subcutaneous tissue, clinical signs, epizootiological analysis, prevention, zoohygiene, antiseptic, biotin, selenium.

Significance of the Study:

Necrobacteriosis is an infectious necrotic ulcerative disease affecting many domestic and wild animals. It is mainly characterized by purulent-necrotic lesions of the skin, mucous membranes, internal organs, and hooves.

Under natural conditions, horses, cattle, buffaloes, deer, sheep, goats, pigs, dogs, cats, poultry (chickens, geese), and wild animals such as brown bears and argali are susceptible.

The source of infection is sick animals or carriers that have recovered but continue to shed the pathogen through feces, mucus, regurgitated material, and necrotic tissues. The natural reservoir is the gastrointestinal tract of healthy animals.

Environmental conditions such as humidity, poor sanitation, and injuries play a crucial role in disease occurrence. The pathogen can persist for long periods in soil, bedding, feed, and equipment, spreading sporadically or epizootically.

Lack of active movement prevents the natural wearing of the hoof wall, resulting in various deformations of hoof shape. When moisture exchange is disrupted, the hoof horn becomes brittle, leading to cracks and fractures. Under dark and humid conditions, the horn layer softens rapidly and deforms under the animal's body weight. In tethered cows, the effect of ammonia often causes rotting of the sole region of the hoof.

The health of cattle largely depends on proper hoof care. The hoof horn grows on average 6–8 mm per month and is completely renewed within 6–10 months. If timely cleaning and trimming are not performed, hoof shape is altered, limb placement changes, and susceptibility to various diseases increases.

One of the main causes of hoof diseases is nutritional deficiency. Keratin — the key substance binding horn cells — is synthesized only under normal metabolic processes involving sulfur. For sulfur metabolism, selenium is essential, and its amount must be balanced with other micro- and macroelements. In addition, vitamins, especially biotin (vitamin B7), are critical for hoof health; deficiency poses a serious risk.

Rumen bacteria normally synthesize sufficient biotin. However, when rumen function is impaired, its production decreases. A diet deficient in fiber and excessive in sugars lowers rumen pH, leading to the loss of certain bacteria. During their breakdown, endotoxins are released, restricting blood circulation in the small vessels of the hooves and reducing nutrient and oxygen supply. This creates favorable conditions for secondary infections, including necrobacteriosis.

In some districts of the Tashkent region, necrobacteriosis has also been recorded among high-yielding dairy cattle. This condition was most often observed in animals kept on straw bedding that was rarely replaced. Such bedding frequently became soaked with urine and contaminated with manure. The concrete floor beneath the bedding did not absorb moisture, thereby creating an environment highly favorable for the spread of infection (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A cow affected by necrobacteriosis

Thus, such conditions create opportunities for the persistence of any source of infection, including the causative agent of necrobacteriosis. In addition, lack of active movement in cows, especially in high-yielding cattle, has a negative impact on overall health. The natural resistance of the organism decreases, the hoof horn becomes deformed, and its integrity is compromised. As a result, cracks form in the hoof, through which the necrobacteriosis pathogen can penetrate into the body.

Purpose of the Study:

To investigate the spread, clinical signs, and development factors of necrobacteriosis in high-yielding cattle, and to develop preventive and effective control measures.

Main Objectives:

In order to study the causes of necrobacteriosis spread, its mechanisms of development, and effective control measures in high-yielding cattle, the following objectives were set:

- Determine the stability of the pathogen under environmental factors (humidity, temperature, feed, soil).
- Analyze housing and management conditions to identify major risk factors.
- Characterize the stages of necrobacteriosis based on clinical and pathomorphological signs.
- Assess the impact of essential biogenic elements (sulfur, selenium, biotin, dietary fiber) on hoof health.
- Improve preventive and therapeutic methods and evaluate their effectiveness under farm conditions.

Materials and Methods

As research objects, high-yielding cattle kept on a farm in the Tashkent region, laboratory animals (white mice), and pathological materials were selected.

The processes of isolating and identifying microorganisms involved in the pathogenesis of necrobacteriosis and hoof diseases were carried out according to Bergey’s classification of bacteria and standard bacteriological methods. In addition, the clinical and epizootiological situation was analyzed based on specialized methodological guidelines and manuals.

For pathomorphological analysis, pathological materials obtained after slaughter — samples from hoof lesions, parenchymal organs (heart, liver, lungs, kidneys), as well as necrotic foci in the stomach and intestinal walls — and tissue samples from damaged hooves of live cattle were used.

All pathological materials were examined using standard bacteriological and mycological methods. To isolate the causative agent of necrobacteriosis, a modified bioassay method was applied, and the pathogen was isolated from laboratory animals. Pathological samples were cultured on Kitt–Tarozzi medium, meat-peptone broth and agar, as well as Sabouraud medium. A diagnosis of necrobacteriosis was confirmed only in cases where the pathogenic strain of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* was isolated.

Pathoanatomical Changes

Pathoanatomical examination was performed on nine cattle subjected to compulsory slaughter. In these animals, the septic form of necrobacteriosis was identified. During life, they exhibited severe emaciation. The mandibular lymph nodes were markedly enlarged, resembling goiter in external appearance.

During examination, the mucous membranes were found to be pale with a bluish tint. The spleen was not enlarged, but structural changes with bluish discoloration were observed, and large necrotic foci were detected on its surface.

Lung tissues were generally preserved, although localized necrotic foci were noted in some animals. No pathological changes were detected in the heart. In two of the nine examined cattle, necrosis of the mammary gland was observed, involving both superficial and deep tissue layers.

Extensive necrotic changes were found in the hoof horn. The necrotic process affected all layers of the hoof horn and extended into deeper tissues. In some cases, the necrosis spread to the muscles, disrupting their structure (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Necrotic changes in the hoof horn

Treatment of Necrobacteriosis

Under farm conditions, treatment of necrobacteriosis was carried out both in groups and individually.

Group treatment:

Affected cattle were kept in specially designated groups and subjected to general preventive and therapeutic measures. Treatment baths were prepared for the animals, using either 10% copper sulfate, zinc sulfate, or 5% formalin solutions. These baths helped reduce inflammation and necrotic processes in the hoof horn and prevented further spread of infection. In addition, during group treatment, the animals' diet was improved and supplemented with vitamins and minerals to enhance overall resistance.

Individual treatment:

This approach was applied to severely affected cattle. The hoof horn and damaged tissues were mechanically cleaned, and necrotic layers were removed. The wound surface was then treated with antiseptic agents such as hydrogen peroxide or chlorhexidine. In cases of deep necrotic lesions, special ointments and dressings were applied locally. Antibiotics Tetralife Advance were administered intramuscularly, effectively preventing systemic spread of the infection.

Composition of the ointment (per 100 ml):

- ASD-3: 20 ml
- Birch tar: 20 ml
- Boric acid (powder): 2–3 g
- Glycerin: 40 ml
- Oxytetracycline (powder): 10 g

Each animal received 40–50 ml of the broad-spectrum antibiotic tetralife advance intramuscularly.

Treated cattle were kept separately under stable sanitary-hygienic conditions and monitored continuously until full recovery.

Veterinary treatment protocol applied on the farm included:

- In cases of necrosis, affected tissues were treated with 10% copper sulfate solution.
- For necrotic foci, a dry mixture of potassium permanganate and copper sulfate in a 1:2 ratio was applied locally.
- This method was performed without bandaging, which accelerated the cleansing of necrotic tissue and enhanced antiseptic action.

Results

Clinical and laboratory investigations conducted on a farm in the Tashkent region revealed the epizootiological status, clinical signs, and pathoanatomical changes of necrobacteriosis in high-yielding cattle.

During the study, necrobacteriosis was mainly observed in tethered cows with limited mobility, kept in humid environments. Under such conditions, bedding was contaminated with manure and urine, creating a favorable environment for infection. The incidence of disease was significantly higher in cases where hoof care was insufficient.

Microbiological analysis confirmed the isolation and identification of the pathogenic strain *Fusobacterium necrophorum* from affected tissues. This bacterium was characterized by its ability to grow well under anaerobic conditions and induce necrotic processes. On Kitt–Tarozzi medium, the isolates grew sufficiently within 48–72 hours, forming characteristic bacterial colonies with gas production and small bubbles.

Pathomorphological analysis revealed necrosis, inflammation, and tissue damage across all layers of the hoof horn. In some cases, the process extended into deeper tissues and muscle layers, accompanied by brittleness and cracking of the hoof horn. Necrotic changes were also detected in the mammary glands of two cows. Enlargement of mandibular lymph nodes and necrotic foci in the spleen were observed, while no significant morphological changes were found in the heart and lungs.

Clinically, affected cows exhibited lameness, cautious movement, slight fever, and reduced appetite. In some cases, foul-smelling exudate was discharged from the affected hooves.

To evaluate treatment efficacy, two approaches were applied: group and individual therapy.

- Group therapy involved the use of 10% copper sulfate and 5% formalin footbaths, combined with vitamin-mineral supplementation. This method limited disease spread and reduced new cases by 40–45%.
- Individual therapy included hoof cleaning, antiseptic treatment (hydrogen peroxide, chlorhexidine), followed by antibiotics and special ointments (ASD-3, birch tar, glycerin, boric acid powder, oxytetracycline powder). Within 7–10 days, wound surfaces were cleansed, inflammation subsided, and locomotor activity was restored.

By the end of the study, the recovery rate reached 87%, with complete cleansing of infected hooves. In the untreated control group, infection persisted, confirming the importance of proper hygiene and management practices.

The findings demonstrated that the main factors influencing the development of necrobacteriosis are high humidity, poor sanitation, nutritional deficiencies (sulfur and biotin), and limited animal mobility. Therefore, the primary preventive strategy is to optimize housing conditions and ensure a balanced diet.

Conclusion

Based on clinical, epizootiological, and laboratory studies, it was established that the spread of necrobacteriosis in high-yielding cattle is strongly influenced by poor housing conditions, excessive humidity, deficiencies of biogenic elements in the diet, and non-compliance with sanitary standards.

In diseased cattle, hoof horn destruction, inflammation of skin and subcutaneous tissues, deep necrotic foci, and painful lameness were observed. Laboratory examinations confirmed *Fusobacterium necrophorum* as the principal causative agent.

The results indicate that prevention of necrobacteriosis requires strict adherence to zoohygienic standards, regular hoof care, and disinfection with antiseptic agents. Furthermore, supplementation of the diet with biotin, selenium, and sulfur compounds strengthens hoof structure and increases resistance to the disease.

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